

Necessary Skills for Employment Generation in Bayelsa State: Perceptions of Undergraduate Business Education Students of Federal University Otuoke.

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Abstract

The study investigated the Necessary Skills for Employment Generation in Bayelsa State: Perceptions of Undergraduate Business Education Students of Federal University Otuoke p. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The targeted population for the study comprised all the 2022/2023 academic session 400 and 300 levels Business Education students in the study area. A sample size of sample size of eighty-eight (88) respondents was selected using the purposive sampling technique for study. The instrument for data collection for the study was a structured questionnaire titled “Necessary Skills for Employment Generation Bayelsa State IQuestionnaire (NSEGBSQ)”. To guide the study, three research questions were raised. The data collected were analysed using simple percentage for the demographic variable and the statistical mean for the research question. The study found that communication skills and problem solving skills in business education are important tools for employment generation in Bayelsa State as perceived by undergraduate students in business education in Federal University, Otuoke. The study therefore concluded and recommended that Government through policy in education should ensure that the curriculum planners incorporate courses in these skilled areas in academic programmes of business education undergraduates which would help them to be better equipped in communication and problem solving skills on graduation.

Keywords: Necessary Skills, Employment, Generation, Perception, Business Education Students.

Introduction

Education is the bedrock of a nation’s economy. It is the suitable legacy with which a child should be left in order to successfully exist in life and to remain productively capable in any economy. Education is also seen to be the robust step in paving the way for the citizenry of a nation to achieve their desired interest in the world of business. Education has also been viewed as the instrument used to impact in-depth knowledge and understanding so as to enable the youths advance to new frontier of knowledge in different walks of life (Enwere, Ugwu, &Olawoyin, 2013). It is not a gain saying that a nation could be bailed from the syndrome of unemployment if a well-tailored

education cum training is provided by the government of a country. One of the educational programs that are available in Nigerian tertiary educational institutions in order to promote self-reliance is Business Education.

Business Education is a type of education that is designed to inculcate in individuals' skills, knowledge, business spirit, and acumen needed to thrive in the world of work and to become self-reliant. Nwaigburu and Eneogwe (2013) opined that Business Education represents a broad and diverse discipline that is included in all types of educational delivery systems, elementary, secondary and tertiary institutions. It includes education for office occupation, distribution, marketing occupations, accounting, business teaching, business administration, business management, typewriting, stenography and secretarial education or studies. Business Education will produce responsible, productive and self-reliant citizens.

A skill as opined by Etonyeaku, Kanu, Ezeji, and Chukwuma (2014) is an ability to perform an activity in a competent manner. A skill is any established habit of performing a task in a way that is acceptable by a worker in his specialization. It is the ability to use one's knowledge effectively and readily in performing an act or a habit of doing a particular task competently (Skills can, 2012). It could therefore be operationalized that skill is the aptitude to handle a particular task in a professional manner towards achieving the desired aim. Certain skills should be acquired by trainees for them to be in self-employment after graduation. Hence Ezenwafor and Olaniyi (2017) asserted that skills for operating a business enterprise are needed for the business to succeed in the competitive market. Some of the skills include time management skills and self-motivation skills. On the other hand, skills acquisition is the ability to learn a skill. It is the practical way of developing and acquiring expertise knowledge, clear-cut competencies and technical knowhow in learners, which they would use to improve the economic frontiers of their immediate society. Practical skill acquisition is an important aspect of business education programme. From the aforementioned contents and objectives of business education curriculum in colleges of education, students are expected to acquire sufficient skills in teaching methodology, office technology and management, entrepreneurship, information and communication technology, Language skill, Managerial skill and accounting/computational skill. The acquisition of these skills stands to enable business education graduates to be self-reliant and contribute to national economic development.

According to Ukata and Edwin (2021), Problem solving refers to finding a way where no way is known, off-hand out of a difficulty around an obstacle. Problem solving is a cognitive processing directed at achieving a goal when no solution is obvious to the problem solver. Problem arises when an individual has a goal but does not know how this goal is to be reached. Problem solving skills refer to the ability to find the cause of a problem, understanding it, and establishing a solution to it. Problem solving skills are demonstrated in the comprehensive process of identifying a problem, generating and implementing solutions, and the assessment of the results (Ann-Marie, 2015). Students and employers consider problem solving skills as important employability skills and by so doing one earn income and create wealth that lift one from poverty. Problem solving skills were the second highest ranked soft skills that technology students needed for successful postsecondary level, as these skills were integral to careers in technology and engineering enable learners to create wealth. Problem solving skills represented one of the generic skills that enhance graduates' employability, employment and further noted that this perspective was a growing trend in higher education for poverty reduction.

Cigar (2017) stated that it is common knowledge that business organizations are always saddled with solving their business problems to achieve organizational goals. Problem-solving skills consist in using generic or ad hoc method in an orderly manner for finding solutions to problems. Problem-solving is a key skill, and it is one that can make a huge difference to one's career with great wealth generation According to Cigar (2017), these skills involve: Ability to identify a problem, ability to plan solution to the problem, ability to evaluate alternative solutions to the problem, ability to implement the solutions, ability to check the result and communicate effectively, ability to show independence in solving a project task, ability to show initiative in solving project task, ability to resolve customer/client concerns in relation to complex project issues, ability to know one's strengths when planning for solution to a problem. With these steps, the Business Education students would be able to handle tough job problems in a wise and positive way to create wealth. The Business Education students need problem-solving skills to apply in the business environment to solve company accounting problems upon graduation. Undergraduates should learn and acquire problem-solving skills.

Developing communication skills and initiative should become major concerns of higher education, in order to facilitate employability of graduates who will increasingly be called upon to be not only job seekers but also and above all to become job creators, (Cephas and Bitrus, 2020). Communication is what keeps the vision alive in entrepreneur's communication with others and himself. Until and unless an idea is given a tangible body, it remains in its abstract form and there are chances that it may vanish. It is in communication that an idea gets envisioned; the moment the idea starts developing into a concrete shape in its communication, an entrepreneur starts visualizing the complete picture.

Communication soft skills are the tools used to clearly and effectively converse with others, set expectations, and work with others on projects in any organisation. It is a form of verbal and written communication used in every day at the working place. Whether for writing a cover letter to apply for a job, taking up an issue with manager, or looking to green light a new initiative at work. Every professional irrespective of their field should be able to convey their thoughts with clarity and confidence both in written and oral forms Oluwalola (2021).

According to Alademerin in Ihimekpen, Crossdale and Amaehule (2015), it involves meeting people and making them buy business ideas, products or services, or meeting people and encouraging them to sell their business ideas, products or services. The graduate of Business Education should have the following skills: good command of English language, possess listening skill, possess intelligent perception skill, competent to make intelligent interpretations, be competent in use of body language, possession of friendly voice and ability to make intelligent selection of communication channels, telephone skill, public speaking skill, positive attitude skill (Oyinlore, Asonibare and Kikelomo, 2021).

Furthermore, according to Cephas and Bitrus (2020), the following communication skills are needed by an undergraduate of OMT and they are: Written communication skills, Verbal communication skill, Non-verbal communication skill, Feedback receiving skill and voice tone skill. These skills are learnt during period of apprenticeship, vocational or technical training, seminars, workshops and on-the-job-training. A worker who lacks communication skills would be using un-refined and uncomplimentary language on customers, workers, suppliers, and friends.

Government of Nigeria (FGN) (2018) asserted that youth unemployment is very serious in Nigeria and other Africa countries. In addition, FGN explained that it has commenced work on a program plan termed "Youth Employment and Skills Development" so as to fight the menace of

unemployment situation in Nigeria. Equipping students with the innovation and adaptation contingent with changes in the world of business that leads to proficiency and efficiency in analyzing and operating business enterprises will enable them fit into the world of work properly. Studying business education courses can give graduates an advantage in their future career upon graduation. This is because even if graduates have a first-class degree and a relevant course for the career they want, they will most likely be competing against others who have the same or similar academic qualifications. Therefore, it is the graduates' employability, the unique mix of skills, abilities and personal qualities that they have, that will make them stand out from the crowd. As the world of work is undergoing a swift change due to technological evolution, the careers of business education graduates are likely to involve many different job roles and employers, and even if they stay in the same job, it is likely to change its nature over time. Therefore, it is against this backdrop this work sought to investigate skills in business education for employment generation in Bayelsa State as perceived by undergraduate students in business education in Federal University, Otuoke.

Statement of the Problem

Some graduates of business education are roaming the streets searching for white collar jobs that are rarely available. This ordeal has resulted to the low level of standard of living in Nigeria. The business education graduates who have gone through the undergraduate program in schools are expected to have acquired self-employment skills such as time management skills, self-motivation skills, interpersonal skills, financial management skills, human resource management skills and customer service skills, etc. that will enable them own and manage their businesses and become employers of labor. With nonexistence of these skills, business education graduates roam about the streets of Nigeria in search for white collar jobs that are not obtainable. Perhaps due to nonexistence of these skills, some business education graduates still roam about the streets of Nigeria in search of white-collar jobs that may not be available.

The above worrisome situation notwithstanding the business education academic programme as it is currently, tend to lack the capacity to impact students needed skills for self-employment. In other words, the existing business education academic programme drawn up for the schools no longer seem to sufficiently contain the needed skills for actualization of successful business activities in the present-day job market.

Therefore, it is against this backdrop this work sought to investigate skills in business education for employment generation in Bayelsa State as perceived by undergraduate students in business education in Federal University, Otuoke.

Purpose of the Study

1. communication skills in business education for employment generation in Bayelsa State as perceived by undergraduate students in business education in Federal University, Otuoke.
2. Problem-solving skills in business education for employment generation in Bayelsa State as perceived by undergraduate students in business education in Federal University, Otuoke.

Research Questions

1. What are the communication skills in business education for employment generation in Bayelsa State as perceived by undergraduate students in business education in Federal University, Otuoke?

2. What are the problem-solving skills in business education for employment generation in Bayelsa State as perceived by undergraduate students in business education in Federal University, Otuoke?

Significance of the Study

The following group of persons would benefit from the findings of the study. They include the teachers, students, curriculum planners, researchers and the society at large. The teachers would realize the need for competence and skillful delivery of lessons to equip learners the requisite skills they need in order to fit into the world of work. Teachers would also realize the skills they lack or are deficient in business education, and thus undertake a rigorous training to acquire the necessary business education skills to upgrade themselves.

The students would equally benefit from the study if implemented, as they would be aware of the skills required in management of their intended business enterprises for a living after schooling. This will make them to be self-reliance and self-sufficient.

The curriculum planners would also benefit from the study. If these skills are fully utilized by teachers and students, it would enable curriculum planners to reform their curriculum in line with the practical needs of the teachers especially in business management and other office related issues. Researchers would use the body of knowledge provided by the study as reference points for further research in the areas of skills required for the teaching and learning of business education in schools.

Finally, the entire society would be better off when teachers and students of business education adopt these skills in the teaching and learning process of the subject. This would enable graduates to adopt such skills for practical business management and other office related issues, thereby making them to be competent and self-reliant, and to beef-up with the economic demands of the society.

Methods

This study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The targeted population of the study consisted all 2022/2023 academic session 400 and 300 levels students of Business Education in Federal University, Otuoke., Bayelsa State. Thus; a total number of one hundred and thirty-one (131) respondents were used for the study. A sample size of eighty-eight (88) respondents, representing about 67% of the total population was purposively selected for the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-designed questionnaire of twenty items using four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 respectively. The entire copies of the instrument were distributed to respondents with the help of a research assistant. Data was analyzed using arithmetic mean for the research questions, with a criterion mean response score of 2.50 on a four-point rating scale. For a decision to be reached, mean scores from 2.50 and above were adjudged agreed, while mean scores 2.49 and below were adjudged disagreed.

Results

Research Question 1:

What are the communication skills in business education for employment generation in Bayelsa State as perceived by undergraduate students in business education in Federal University, Otuoke?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Students for research question one

S/N	Items	SD	A	D	SD	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1.	Ability to tailor conversation to suit various audience	33	29	23	3	88	3.05	0.88	Agree
2	Ability to speak clearly without mumbling	21	36	19	12	88	2.75	0.97	Agree
3	Ability to sustain discussion for a long time.	30	28	15	15	88	2.83	1.00	Agree
4	Ability to tolerate staff or customers of aggressive disposition	31	26	21	10	88	2.89	1.20	Agree
5	Public speaking and Body language skills.	29	31	24	4	88	2.99	0.89	Agree
Grand Mean and Standard Deviation							2.90	0.99	Agree

Source: Field Survey Data, 2024

Table 1: It revealed that all the items had their mean scores ranged from 2.75 to 3.05 with their standard deviation from 0.88 to 1.20 respectively, which is greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50. However, despite the fact that the grand mean of 2.90 with a standard deviation of 0.99 which is greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50, it therefore implies that respondents agreed that all the items are communication skills in business education for employment generation in Bayelsa State as perceived by undergraduate students in business education in Federal University, Otueke.

Research question 2:

What are the problem-solving skills in business education for employment generation in Bayelsa State as perceived by undergraduate students in business education in Federal University, Otueke?

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Teachers and Students for research question two

S/N	Items	SD	A	D	SD	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1.	Ability to gather information and develop courses of action during decision making process.	33	29	23	3	88	3.05	0.88	Agree
2	Ability to analyze and compare courses of action (alternatives/solutions).	21	36	19	12	88	2.75	0.97	Agree
3	Ability to identify, recognize and define the problem at hand.	30	28	15	15	88	2.83	1.00	Agree
4	Ability to critically analyze situations before taking decision in the office.	31	26	21	10	88	2.89	1.20	Agree
5	Patience is required in taking effective decision in the modern offices.	29	31	24	4	88	2.99	0.89	Agree
Grand Mean and Standard Deviation							2.90	0.99	Agree

Source: Field Survey Data, 2024

Table 2: It revealed that all the items had their mean scores ranged from 2.75 to 3.05 with their standard deviation from 0.88 to 1.20 respectively, which is greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50. However, despite the fact that the grand mean of 2.90 with a standard deviation of 0.99 which is greater than the criterion mean score of 2.50, it therefore implies that respondents agreed that all the items are problem solving skills in business education for employment generation in Bayelsa State as perceived by undergraduate students in business education in Federal University, Otuoke.

Discussion of Findings

The discussions of findings follow as they appear. From the results, it was revealed that all the statements are communication skills in business education for employment generation in Bayelsa State as perceived by undergraduate students in business education in Federal University, Otuoke. Therefore, the communication skills needed are Ability to tailor conversation to suit various audiences, ability to speak clearly without mumbling, ability to sustain discussion for a long time, ability to tolerate staff or customers of aggressive disposition, public speaking and body language skills. This further shows how communication skills in business education are important in generating employment in Bayelsa State. The finding is in accordance with Ejeka (2021) that communication skills were highly required of Business graduate for effective performance. Also the study of Ezechukwu, Oliver, Muhammadu and Ayoola (2021) found amongst others that communication skills needed but was lacking in OTM graduates.

Also, the study found that all the statements are problem-solving skills in business education for employment generation in Bayelsa State as perceived by undergraduate students in business education in Federal University, Otuoke. Problem-solving is ability to define a problem, generate alternatives, evaluate and select the alternatives and implement solutions to them. These problem solving skills required are: ability to gather information and develop courses of action during decision making process, ability to analyze and compare courses of action (alternatives/solutions), ability to identify, recognize and define the problem at hand, ability to critically analyze situations before taking decision in the office., patience is required in taking effective decision in the modern offices. According to Imeokparia and Ediagbonya (2019), it is a set of activities designed to analyze a situation systematically and generate, implement, and evaluate solutions. The authors insisted that problem solving is critically an important skill area for administrators, planners, voluntary agency coordinators, and other professional managers. A well skilled and equipped Business Education graduate should in addition be creative so as to be employable in this technological era.

Conclusion

The empirical evidence does show that communication skills and problem solving skills in Business Education are important tools for employment generation in Bayelsa State as perceived by undergraduate students in business education in Federal University, Otuoke.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following were recommended amongst others:

1. Government through policy in education should ensure that the curriculum planners incorporate courses in these skilled areas in academic programmes of business education undergraduates which would help them to be better equipped in communication and problem solving skills on graduation.
2. Teaching and learning in business education should be more practice rather than theory.

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